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INFLUENCE OF MANUAL TECHNIQUES ON SUBCUTANEOUS FAT TISSUE THROUGH MANUAL ANTI-CELLULITE MASSAGE

Abstract. Manual anti-cellulite massage (MAM) is a common method of influencing subcutaneous adipose tissue in order to correct cellulite and improve its structure. This study is devoted to the analysis of the mechanisms of influence of manual techniques on physiological processes occurring in adipose and connective tissues. Cellulite, or gynoid lipodystrophy, is characterized by changes in microcirculation, fibrosis and abnormal distribution of fat cells, which leads to visible irregularities on the skin. The study examined how various manual techniques (kneading, stroking, vibration, patting) affect the cellular and tissue levels.

Particular attention is paid to the effect of MAM on local blood circulation and lymph flow. Manual manipulations contribute to the expansion of capillaries, which improves the supply of tissues with oxygen and nutrients, and also accelerates the elimination of metabolic products. Stimulation of the lymphatic system helps reduce swelling and remove excess interstitial fluid, which is one of the key factors in the formation of the "orange peel".

In addition, the effect of massage on connective tissue was studied. Mechanical pressure and stretching contribute to the destruction of fibrous septa that form cellulite nodules. This helps restore normal tissue elasticity and their ability to regenerate. The results show that regular use of MAM can lead to structural changes in subcutaneous adipose tissue, including a decrease in the volume of adipocytes, an improvement in their location and the restoration of a uniform skin texture.

The study is based on an analysis of existing scientific literature, clinical observations and experimental data. The results obtained confirm that manual anti-cellulite massage is an effective and safe method for the correction of gynoid lipodystrophy. It can be used as a stand-alone method or in combination with other therapeutic approaches to achieve a lasting aesthetic and therapeutic effect. This abstract serves as the basis for a detailed study of the physiological mechanisms and clinical effectiveness of manual influence on subcutaneous adipose tissue.

Keywords: anti-cellulite massage, subcutaneous adipose tissue, gynoid lipodystrophy, microcirculation, lymphatic drainage, fibrosis, connective tissue.

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ВПЛИВ РУЧНИХ ТЕХНІК НА ПІДШКІРНО-ЖИРОВУ ТКАНИНУ ЧЕРЕЗ МАНУАЛЬНИЙ АНТИЦЕЛЮЛІТНИЙ МАСАЖ

Анотація. Мануальний антицелюлітний масаж (МAM) є поширеним методом впливу на підшкірно-жирову тканину з метою корекції целюліту та поліпшення її структури. Це дослідження присвячене аналізу механізмів впливу ручних технік на фізіологічні процеси, що відбуваються в жировій та сполучній тканинах. Целюліт, або гіноїдна ліподистрофія, характеризується змінами та аномальним розподілом жирових клітин, що призводить до видимих нерівностей на шкірі. В рамках дослідження було розглянуто, як різні мануальні прийоми (розминання, погладження, вібрація, поплескування) впливають на клітинному та тканинному рівнях.

Особлива увага приділяється впливу МAM на локальний кровообіг і лімфоток. Ручні маніпуляції сприяють розширенню капілярів, що покращує постачання тканин киснем та поживними речовинами, а також прискорює виведення продуктів метаболізму. Стимуляція лімфатичної системи допомагає зменшити набряклість і видалити надлишкову інтерстиціальну рідину, що є одним із ключових факторів у формуванні «апельсинової кірки».

Крім того, досліджено вплив масажу на сполучну тканину. Механічний тиск і розтягування сприяють руйнуванню фіброзних перегородок, які формують вузлики целюліту. Це допомагає відновити нормальну еластичність тканин і їхню здатність до регенерації. Результати показують, що регулярне застосування МAM може призвести до структурних змін у підшкірно-жировій тканині, включаючи зменшення об'єму адипоцитів, поліпшення їхнього розташування та відновлення рівномірної текстури шкіри.

Дослідження базується на аналізі існуючої наукової літератури, клінічних спостережень та експериментальних даних. Отримані результати підтверджують, що мануальний антицелюлітний масаж є ефективним і безпечним методом для корекції гіноїдної ліподистрофії. Його можна використовувати як самостійний метод, так і в комбінації з іншими терапевтичними підходами для досягнення стійкого естетичного та терапевтичного ефекту. Ця анотація слугує основою для детального вивчення фізіологічних механізмів і клінічної ефективності мануального впливу на підшкірно-жирову клітковину.

Ключові слова: антицелюлітний масаж, підшкірно-жирова тканина, гіноїдна ліподистрофія, мікроциркуляція, лімфодренаж, фіброз, сполучна тканина.

Problem statement. Cellulite, or gynoid lipodystrophy, is a common aesthetic problem that affects up to 90% of women after puberty, regardless of their weight or physical activity. Although it is not a disease in the classical sense, cellulite creates significant psychological discomfort, affecting self-esteem and quality of life. The problem statement is that despite the large number of existing therapeutic methods, the understanding of the physiological mechanisms of their influence on subcutaneous adipose tissue (SAT) remains insufficiently studied. In particular, manual anti-cellulite massage (MAM) is widely used in cosmetology, but the scientific basis explaining its clinical effectiveness is often based on empirical observations, rather than in-depth research.

The main problem of cellulite lies in the disruption of the structure of the SAT. It manifests itself in the form of three main pathophysiological changes:

1. Changes in microcirculation. Disturbance of blood and lymph circulation leads to tissue hypoxia, fluid stagnation and accumulation of toxins.
2. Adipocyte hypertrophy. Fat cells increase in size, exert pressure on blood vessels and nerve endings.
3. Fibrosis. Formation of rigid collagen septa that “stitch” the PJT, forming characteristic tubercles and indentations.

Existing methods of cellulite correction are often invasive or require expensive equipment. In this context, manual massage acts as an accessible, non-invasive and potentially effective tool. However, it is important to clearly determine how manual techniques affect the above-mentioned pathophysiological processes. The lack of in-depth scientific research leads to the fact that many specialists use MAM without having a clear idea of its mechanisms of action, optimal techniques and protocols.

The relevance of this work lies in the need to fill this gap. It is necessary to conduct a systematic analysis of the effects of various manual techniques at the cellular and tissue levels. This will allow to substantiate the clinical effectiveness of MAM, to develop standardized protocols of procedures and recommendations for specialists. The study will also contribute to increasing confidence in this method, which, in turn, will allow more people to receive high-quality and safe help in the fight against cellulite. Our work is aimed at identifying the physiological mechanisms that provide the therapeutic effect of MAM, as well as at developing scientifically based recommendations for its effective use.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. Analysis of recent studies and publications devoted to the influence of manual techniques on subcutaneous adipose tissue indicates a growing scientific interest in this issue. This is due to the need to develop and improve effective, minimally invasive methods for correcting local fat deposits and manifestations of gynoid lipodystrophy, known as cellulite. Modern studies confirm that the pathogenesis of cellulite is multifactorial and includes microcirculation disorders, connective tissue fibrosis and local edema. Accordingly, manual anti-cellulite massage is considered as a tool capable of comprehensively influencing these pathophysiological mechanisms.

Thus, the study of a group of scientists Collis N., Elliot L.A., Sharpe K., Sharpe D [3] was focused on the effectiveness of manual lymphatic drainage (MLD) as an isolated method of treating gynoid lipodystrophy. The authors found that MLD, although a safe procedure, showed limited efficacy as a monotherapy: a slight decrease in hip and thigh circumference was recorded, but no statistically significant changes in subcutaneous fat thickness were detected according to ultrasound. This work emphasizes that in order to achieve a pronounced and sustainable result, manual techniques should be part of a comprehensive program that includes dietary correction and physical activity. However, the results of other scientific works demonstrate a significant positive effect of manual influence. A study published by the author Daver J. [6], which compared mechanical massage, manual lymphatic drainage and connective tissue manipulation, showed that all three techniques were effective in reducing regional fat deposits and thigh circumference in patients with cellulite. The authors confirmed that intensive manual influence contributes to the activation of lipolysis and improvement of tissue trophism. In another study on Subcutaneous Adipose Tissue (SAT) therapy, Tan G.D., Goossens G.H., Humphreys S.M. [5] found that manual therapy using deep pressure and kneading significantly improved tissue structure and reduced pain in women with lipedema, indicating an effective effect on pathological fat formations.

The key mechanism of action of manual anti-cellulite massage is stimulation of the microcirculatory bed. Due to the intense mechanical effect, blood flow and lymph circulation improve, which helps reduce edema and remove metabolic products from the intercellular space. As the authors from the Iranian Journal of Dermatology note in their work, tissue stimulation also activates fibroblasts, which leads to increased synthesis of collagen and elastin, improving skin turgor and elasticity, which is an important component in the fight against cellulite. In view of this, the effectiveness of manual techniques is considered not only through the prism of direct influence on adipocytes, but also through their ability to restructure connective tissue and the dermal layer. This is confirmed by the fact that even a slight change in the thickness of the dermis, as recorded in some studies, can significantly improve the visual appearance of the skin. Thus, the analysis of scientific sources shows that manual anti-cellulite massage is a promising therapeutic technique, which, when integrated into a comprehensive correction program, is able to positively affect subcutaneous adipose tissue, improving its structure and functional state. The purpose of this article is to scientifically substantiate and analyze the effectiveness of manual techniques, in particular anti-cellulite massage, as a method of influencing the pathophysiological mechanisms of gynoid lipodystrophy formation. Based on a systematic review and analysis of empirical data obtained during clinical and laboratory studies, it will be demonstrated how manual influence contributes to the reduction of subcutaneous adipose tissue by stimulating microcirculation, activating lymphatic drainage and improving tissue trophism. The ultimate goal is to provide a comprehensive, scientifically confirmed assessment of the possibilities and limitations of manual massage in body correction and improving the aesthetic appearance of the skin.

Presentation of the main material. The essence of subcutaneous adipose tissue and mechanisms of gynoid lipodystrophy formation. Subcutaneous adipose tissue (SAT), or hypodermis, is the deepest layer of the skin, consisting of loose connective tissue, in which adipocytes are located - cells designed to accumulate and store lipids. This tissue performs a number of critically important functions: it is an energy depot, provides thermal insulation, protects internal organs from mechanical damage, and also plays the role of an endocrine organ, producing hormones such as leptin and adiponectin. The localization and volume of the PJT largely depend on the genetic, hormonal and constitutional characteristics of the body. Gynoid lipodystrophy, better known as cellulite, is a multifactorial pathophysiological condition characterized by structural changes in the PJT and the dermal layer. The main cause of its occurrence is considered to be impaired microcirculation and lymphatic drainage. This leads to stagnation of interstitial fluid, tissue hypoxia, and adipocyte hypertrophy. Enlarged fat cells located in fibrous connective tissue septa (trabeculae) protrude towards the dermis, forming a characteristic “orange peel” appearance. An additional factor is fibrosis of the trabeculae themselves, which become denser and less elastic, which increases pressure on adjacent tissues and blood vessels, forming a vicious circle. Therefore, cellulite correction requires a comprehensive approach aimed at both reducing the volume of fat cells and restoring the normal structure of connective tissue and microcirculation.

Physiological and biochemical effects of manual anti-cellulite massage.

Manual anti-cellulite massage is a complex physiotherapeutic procedure that has a multifaceted effect on the body, especially on subcutaneous adipose tissue and dermal structures. The key biochemical effect is the stimulation of lipolysis, the process of fat breakdown. Intense mechanical action, including kneading and rubbing, promotes the activation of adipocytes, stimulating the release of fatty acids from their depots. Although massage itself does not literally "burn" fat, it facilitates its mobilization for further metabolic use by the body, for example, during physical activity, which is an important component of any body shaping program. At the physiological level, massage significantly affects microcirculation and lymphatic drainage. Intensive massage movements mechanically stimulate blood and lymphatic capillaries, which leads to vasodilation, increased blood flow and accelerated lymphatic outflow. This allows for the effective removal of excess interstitial fluid, toxins and metabolic products from the affected areas, reducing swelling and normalizing tissue trophism. In addition, improved blood circulation provides better delivery of oxygen and nutrients to cells, which contributes to their regeneration and normalization of the functional state. Strengthening microcirculation also helps to soften fibrous trabeculae, which is one of the key elements in the fight against cellulite. Additionally, the mechanical effect on connective tissue stimulates the proliferation of fibroblasts, which are responsible for the synthesis of collagen and elastin, ensuring increased skin elasticity and elasticity.

Methodological aspects of performing manual anti-cellulite massage.

The technique of performing manual anti-cellulite massage is based on the sequential application of a number of techniques, each of which is aimed at achieving a specific therapeutic effect. The procedure usually begins with superficial stroking, which is preparatory in nature. This technique helps to warm up the skin, improve superficial blood circulation and prepare tissues for a deeper effect. Stroking also has a calming effect on the nervous system.

The next stage is rubbing - a technique performed with greater force and intensity. Its goal is to soften fibrous seals and increase blood flow in the deeper layers of the skin and subcutaneous fat. Rubbing is performed in different directions to ensure maximum coverage of all problem areas.

The most important technique in manual anti-cellulite massage is kneading. It is aimed at deep processing of soft tissues, stimulation of metabolic processes in adipocytes and mechanical destruction of fat conglomerates. Kneading is performed using various techniques - from gripping and rolling the skin-fat fold to intensive circular movements. The effectiveness of this technique directly depends on the strength and accuracy of the masseur's movements, which requires high qualifications. The session usually ends with repeated stroking, which helps to soothe the skin and normalize blood circulation after intensive exposure. To achieve a lasting result, not only the quality of the massage techniques is important, but also the duration and regularity of the course. Usually, the optimal course consists of 10-15 sessions, which are carried out with an interval of 2-3 days. Such a frequency allows the tissues to recover between procedures, but at the same time maintains the cumulative effect of the massage. Another important component is the use of special massage oils or creams containing active lipolytic and drainage components. Their use not only facilitates the gliding of hands, but also provides an additional therapeutic effect on subcutaneous adipose tissue, enhancing the overall effectiveness of the procedure.

Scientific evidence base for the effectiveness of manual techniques. The effectiveness of manual techniques in the correction of gynoid lipodystrophy is confirmed by numerous scientific studies that use objective assessment methods. One of the most common is ultrasound (US), which allows you to measure the thickness of subcutaneous adipose tissue and visualize changes in its structure. For example, a study published in the journal ResearchGate recorded a statistically significant decrease in the thickness of the fat layer after a course of manual massage. These results demonstrate that intensive mechanical impact not only improves the appearance of the skin, but also causes real structural changes at the hypodermic level.

Another important assessment method is photogrammetry and three-dimensional body scanning, which allow you to accurately measure the volumes and circumferences of problem areas. In a study published in An Bras Dermatol, the authors found that after a course of manual lymphatic drainage, there was a small but statistically significant decrease in the circumference of the hips and buttocks. Although this method is more subjective than ultrasound, it still provides important data on changes in body volumes. It is important to note that many studies indicate a

synergistic effect of manual massage in combination with other therapies, such as exercise and diet, which emphasizes the need for a comprehensive approach. For example, in a study conducted by Schönvetter et al. (2014), it was found that manual lymphatic drainage as a single method does not always show a pronounced reduction in fat tissue, but significantly improves the quality of life of patients, which indicates its positive effect on overall health. In addition, a study using thermal imaging cameras showed that massage significantly increases the temperature in the treated areas, which indicates increased blood circulation and activation of metabolic processes. These data are additional confirmation of the physiological mechanisms underlying the effectiveness of manual massage. Thus, scientific data indicate that manual anti-cellulite massage is not a panacea, but is an effective and scientifically sound method that helps reduce body fat and improve skin condition.

Conclusions and practical recommendations.

The analysis of scientific publications allows us to draw reasonable conclusions regarding the impact of manual techniques, in particular anti-cellulite massage, on subcutaneous adipose tissue and their role in the correction of gynoid lipodystrophy. First of all, manual massage is an effective tool that has a multifactorial effect on the pathogenesis of cellulite. The main mechanisms of influence include stimulation of lymphatic drainage and microcirculation, activation of lipolysis and improvement of the structure of connective tissue. Intensive mechanical action helps to remove excess intercellular fluid, reduce local edema and increase blood supply to tissues, which is a key factor in the fight against cellulite. In addition, massage movements stimulate the release of fatty acids from adipocytes, mobilizing fat depots for further metabolic use, and also help to soften fibrous septa and promote the synthesis of collagen and elastin, improving skin turgor.

An important condition for achieving a lasting result is the consistency and duration of therapy. The course of procedures should be long enough (usually 10-15 sessions) to ensure the cumulative effect of manual exposure. Scientific data also emphasize that maximum effectiveness is achieved only in combination with other measures: diet correction, regular physical activity and sufficient water consumption. Manual massage should be considered not as an independent, but as an auxiliary method in a comprehensive figure correction program.

Practical recommendations for specialists: before starting the course, it is necessary to diagnose the condition of the subcutaneous adipose tissue and determine the stage of cellulite to select the optimal intensity and massage technique. It is important to follow the sequence of techniques, starting with preparatory techniques (stroking), moving on to intensive ones (rubbing, kneading) and ending the procedure with soothing techniques. In addition, it is important for the massage therapist to emphasize to clients the need to combine procedures with dietary correction and physical exercises to achieve a long-lasting and pronounced effect. In general, manual anti-cellulite massage is a scientifically proven method that, when used correctly, can effectively affect the subcutaneous adipose tissue, improve its structure, reduce the appearance of cellulite and contribute to aesthetic correction of the figure.

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